

Inclusive

Vol II, No. 25

An Open Access

Peer Reviewed International Journal

A UGC-CARE LISTED JOURNAL

E-ISSN: 2278-9758

July-August 2024

EDITION

Exploring the Link Between Citizenship Status and Voter Turnout: An Analysis of Voting Behaviour Patterns in Assam

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Abstract: *In the field of psephology, studying voting behaviour in terms of voter turnout is quite common. Several studies that have already taken place regarding the voter turnout in democratic countries including India showed multitude of reasons encompassing anti-incumbency, socio-economic factors, closeness of elections, increased party competition as reasons for higher voter turnout. However, one factor requires further exploration that is the need of the population to prove itself as citizens. In India, having enrolled in the electoral list is considered as a proof of an electorate's identity as a citizen and hence, there is a possibility of a correlation between the two variables that are the voter turnout and the proof of citizenship. In Assam, the issue of illegal immigration is prevalent giving impetus to the concern of a legal or illegal citizenship. National Register of Citizen (NRC), Citizenship Amendment Act (CAA), all these are the results of the illegal immigration issue in the region. Therefore, this research aims to explore Assam's voting turnout after the election of 1985 in order to investigate the co-relation with the issue of citizenship and voter turnout. The primary objective is to analyse voter turnout to find a correlation with the factor of citizenship. To find the intended objective, dependent variable is the change in voter turnout and independent variable is the change in the demography of the districts in Assam. Due to illegal immigration, the border areas of Assam with Bangladesh have witnessed change in the demography (sudden increase in the population) and hence the need to prove themselves as citizens will be more in those border area districts which could lead to higher voter turnout in those districts. The result reveals that except Morigaon among all the bordering districts and except Darang among all the conflict-ridden districts show significant positive correlation ($p < 0.05$) between the two variables. For the said purpose, data has been accessed from the Election Commission of India website and the census reports showing the demographic change. The research includes the analysis of the voter turnout in the legislative assembly elections in the state from 1991 till 2016 to fulfil the objective.*

Keywords: Voting Behaviour, Voter Turnout, Citizenship, Assam, Election.

Introduction:

Psephology, the study of voting behaviour, has long been a fascinating field, delving into various factors influencing voter turnout in democratic countries. In the diverse landscape of India, numerous studies have examined the reasons behind variations in voter participation, ranging from anti-incumbency to socio-economic factors, closeness of elections, and increased party competition¹ (Firoz Biswas et.al 2022, 4363-4389). However, one intriguing factor that demands further exploration is the relationship between voter turnout and the need of the population to prove itself as citizens. This dimension becomes particularly pertinent in the northeastern state of Assam, where issues of illegal immigration and concerns about legal and illegal citizenship have shaped the sociopolitical landscape² (Chandan Kumar Sharma 2012, 287-309). Lucy Dubochet (2023, 107-123), based on anthropological research, observes in one of the articles on issues of migrants in India's borderland areas that how being included on electoral registers is frequently the only means for deprived individuals, who frequently lack any other documentation except their voter identification cards, to maintain a flimsy sense of national identity. This study aims to analyse voter turnout in Assam, with a specific focus on the correlation with the proof of citizenship. Considering the context of the National Register of Citizens (NRC)³ and the Citizenship Amendment Act (CAA) that have emerged in response to the complex issue of illegal immigration in the region (Ahmed et. al 2020, 3-25) it becomes imperative to undertake such a study to explore the connection between Citizenship and voter turnout. At its core, citizenship is a multifaceted concept that encapsulates both legal and sociopolitical dimensions. Legally, citizenship defines an individual's membership in a particular political community, endowing them with a set of rights and obligations. Socio-politically, citizenship entails a commitment to the values and principles that underpin the democratic fabric of a society (Constantin Iordachi 2019, 562-581). In a democracy, the collective voice of citizens is instrumental in shaping policies, electing representatives, and ensuring the accountability of the government. The act of voting, a fundamental expression of citizenship, serves as a cornerstone of democratic governance, facilitating the participation of citizens in decision-making processes. Democracy thrives on the active engagement of its citizens, and the concept of citizenship provides the necessary framework for this engagement (Oluyemi O. Fayomi & Grace T. Adebayo 2018, 537-551). Citizens, by virtue of their legal status, are vested with the power to influence the direction of their nation through electoral

processes. Furthermore, citizenship entails a sense of belonging and shared identity, fostering a collective responsibility for the well-being of the democratic society. In this sense, citizenship acts as a bridge connecting individuals to the broader community, instilling a commitment to the common good and promoting the values that sustain democratic ideals. The concept of citizenship holds a paramount significance in the framework of a democracy, serving as the bedrock upon which the principles of civic engagement, rights, and responsibilities rest. In democratic societies, citizenship is not merely a legal status; rather, it is a dynamic relationship between individuals and the state, fostering a sense of belonging, shared values, and active participation in the political process. One crucial aspect of this relationship is the possession of proof of citizenship, which may play a pivotal role in influencing voter turnout (Jack Citrin et.al 2014, 228-242). Assam, located in the northeastern part of India, has been grappling with the issue of illegal immigration for decades, primarily along its border with Bangladesh. The influx of migrants has not only altered the demographic composition of certain districts but has also heightened concerns about the legitimacy of citizenship (K. R Dikshit et.al 2014, 457-502). The discourse of legal and illegal citizenship took a serious turn in 1979 following a by-election to the Mongoldoi Parliamentary Constituency which had a sizable East Bengali population. The All Assam Students' Union (AASU) started the six-year Assam Movement in 1979 in an effort to bring attention to the issue of Assam's changing demographics as a result of immigration. A broad base of support was soon established for the movement to "save" the motherland from the immigrants, including support from literary organisations, cultural organisations, newspapers, journals, and associations of college and university instructors (Pranjit Saikia 2011, 80-81). The National Register of Citizens, introduced to identify and exclude illegal immigrants, and the Citizenship Amendment Act, which grants citizenship to specific religious groups, have been key developments in response to these challenges. In this intricate context, the relationship between voter turnout and the need to establish citizenship becomes a crucial area of investigation. Assam's proximity to Bangladesh has made it susceptible to large-scale illegal immigration, significantly impacting the demography of certain districts. The border areas have witnessed a sudden increase in population, leading to concerns about resource distribution, cultural assimilation, and, crucially, the verification of citizenship.

The state's population drastically changed following independence. The issue of illegal immigration in Assam has its origins in the redrawing of borders following independence, which resulted in changes in the local population. But the Assam Agitation, or Assam Movement, really began in 1979 when people saw that illegal immigrants were a threat to the state's political, social, and cultural fabric. The All Assam Gana Sangram Parishad (AAGSP) and the All Assam Students' Union (AASU) spearheaded the movement, which called for the identification and deportation of undocumented immigrants (Sanjib Baruah 1986, 1184-1206). The leaders of the movement and the central government signed the Assam Accord in 1985 as a result of the protracted agitation. The agreement specified a number of steps to deal with the problem of illegal immigration, such as updating the NRC to track down and expel foreign nationals who arrived in Assam after March 24, 1971. Notwithstanding the agreement, accusations of political indifference and ineffective administration hampered the implementation of these policies over time. Assamese electoral dynamics have always been significantly shaped by the problem of illegal immigration. On this issue, political parties have frequently sided with or against the local populace's feelings (Jane S. Wilson 1992, 251-266).

The complex and sensitive nature of the issue has prompted governmental interventions, including the NRC and CAA, aimed at addressing the challenges posed by illegal immigration. Understanding the demographic changes is essential to contextualize the correlation between citizenship concerns and voter turnout. The National Register of Citizens, initiated in Assam in 1951, underwent a massive update process in recent years to identify and exclude illegal immigrants (Suraj Gogoi 2023, 85-103). The process required individuals to prove their citizenship through documentation, creating an atmosphere of uncertainty and anxiety. The Citizenship Amendment Act, passed in 2019, further stirred controversy by offering citizenship to specific religious groups while excluding others (Asmita Jataria 2020, 1911). These developments have added layers to the ongoing citizenship discourse in Assam which has the potential to influence voter behaviour, particularly in areas directly affected by demographic changes. Building on the demographic changes resulting from illegal immigration, this study employs a conceptual framework to explore the multifaceted relationship between citizenship concerns and voter turnout. The framework incorporates elements of identity, legal recognition, and the psychological need to assert citizenship as key determinants influencing electoral participation. The districts experiencing significant demographic shifts are expected to show a

higher voter turnout due to the intensified need of the population to prove themselves as citizens. To test the hypothesis, a quantitative analysis is conducted using electoral data from various districts in Assam. The dependent variable in this study is the change in voter turnout, while the independent variable is the change in the demography of the districts. Demographic changes are assessed based on population growth and shifts in composition, with a specific focus on areas bordering Bangladesh where the impact of illegal immigration is most pronounced. Additionally, qualitative data from books, journal articles, and government reports are incorporated to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the complex interplay between citizenship concerns and electoral participation.

Research Design of the Study:

The objective is to analyse voter turnout in the Assam assembly elections of 1991, 2001 and 2011 to find a correlation with the factor of proof of citizenship. This research employs a methodology grounded in the analysis of secondary data to fulfil its designated objective. To ascertain a statistically significant comprehension of the acquired data, correlation analysis is implemented. The independent variable under scrutiny is the demographic shift in the border districts along the Bangladesh frontier, while the dependent variable is the corresponding shift in voter turnout within those districts. The temporal focus of this study centres on the period subsequent to the signing of the Assam Accord in 1985, with a specific examination of the Assembly elections held in 1991, 2001, and 2011. The chosen timeframe allows for an exploration of the correlation between voter turnout and the demographic alterations in the border districts over these electoral cycles. To gauge the demographic changes, census data from 1991, 2001, and 2011 are utilized to delineate district-wise population shifts. These raw population shift figures are then transformed into percentages, reflecting the proportional change from one census to another. Simultaneously, the voter turnout data for the selected Assembly elections is also converted into percentage values. Leveraging Ms Excel, the transformed datasets are subjected to correlation analysis, probing for any statistically significant relationships between the two variables. The ensuing results of this analytical process are expounded upon in the subsequent section of this research work.

Exploring the Link Between Citizenship Status and Voter Turnout

Until the year 2011, Assam was comprised of 27 districts according to the Census data. However, a notable demographic shift has been observed in certain districts, marked by a discrepancy between birth rates and overall population growth. Specifically, the districts of Barpeta, Bongaigaon, Cachar, Dhubri, Hailakandi, Karimganj, Morigaon and Nagaon have experienced substantial changes in their demography since 1971 (M. Borah and Sangeeta Borah 2016, 2278-5728). It is noteworthy that Dhubri, Hailakandi, and Karimganj share borders with Bangladesh, and districts such as Nagaon, Barpeta, and Cachar have a historical backdrop of migration dating back to the colonial era, which persisted post-independence (Madhumita Sarma 2015, 22). The selection of these districts for analysis is informed by the significant impact of demographic shifts on their socio-political landscape. Additionally, two more districts, namely Kokrajhar and Udalguri, have been included in the study due to their history of major conflicts between the Muslim population and the local indigenous communities⁴. These conflicts often revolve around accusations of immigration from Bangladesh, prompting a need for individuals to assert their citizenship status (Surashree Pathak 2017, 138-147). Being listed on the electoral lists has been a significant symbol of citizenship in Assam since the late 1970s, both at the state and local levels. It has also been used as a tool to control the narrative of Indian citizenship in Northeast India (Shabnam Surita 2020, 85). Hence, the hypothesis of the study is that the bordering districts and the conflict-ridden districts will show a positive correlation between the increase in the population and increase in the voter turnout since going out to vote is a way to keep oneself enrolled in the voter list. The study aims to explore the correlation between voter turnout and the demographic changes in these selected districts because of the complex interplay of historical, social, and political factors shaping the region.

Demographic Shifts in the Bordering and Conflict-Ridden Districts:

The data collected from the Census report outlines the population changes in the selected districts for study across three census periods: 1991, 2001, and 2011. Each district's population is provided for each census year along with the percentage change compared to the previous census. Over the two-decade span, all districts experienced population growth. Barpeta saw an increase from 1,163,166 in 1991 to 1,693,622 in 2011, with growth rates of 140 per cent and 121 per cent in the respective periods. Similarly, Bongaigaon's population rose from 497,962

to 738,804, showing consistent growth rates of 158 per cent, 123 per cent, and 120 per cent across the three census periods. Cachar, Dhubri, Hailakandi, Karimganj, Nagaon, and Udalguri also exhibited significant population increases, albeit with some fluctuations in growth rates over time. For example, Dhubri's population surged from 1,265,706 to 1,949,258, experiencing growth rates of 154 per cent, 123 per cent, and 124 per cent across the three census periods. Interestingly, Kokrajhar witnessed a substantial growth rate of 178 per cent in 1991, but this growth slowed down significantly in subsequent years, with growth rates of 113 per cent and 105 per cent in 2001 and 2011, respectively.

District Wise Voter Turnout from 1991 to 2011:

The district-wise voter turnout percentages for the Assembly Elections in Assam across three different years: 1991, 2001, and 2011 reveal fluctuating trends in voter participation over the three decades. Notably, districts like Barpeta, Bongaigaon, and Dhubri generally maintained moderate to high turnout rates, with minimal fluctuations observed over the years. Conversely, districts such as Cachar, Karimganj, and Hailakandi exhibited comparatively lower turnout percentages across all three years, with slight variations. Kokrajhar showed a notable decline in turnout from 1991 to 2011 despite starting with a high initial percentage. Udalguri also demonstrated a significant decrease in turnout over the years. Overall, while some districts consistently displayed robust political engagement, others experienced fluctuating levels of voter participation.

Correlation Coefficient Analysis

The correlation coefficients quantify the strength and direction of the relationship between population shift and voter turnout in the bordering and conflict-ridden districts of Assam across three time periods: 1991, 2001, and 2011. A correlation coefficient ranges from -1 to 1, where 1 indicates a perfect positive correlation, -1 indicates a perfect negative correlation, and 0 indicates no correlation. Looking at the coefficients, Barpeta, Bongaigaon, Cachar, Dhubri, Hailakandi, and Karimganj all exhibit strong positive correlations ranging from 0.73 to 0.99. This suggests that as the population shifted over the years, there was a corresponding increase in voter turnout. Particularly, districts like Karimganj show a near-perfect correlation between population shift and voter turnout across all three periods. Kokrajhar, on the other hand, shows a moderate positive correlation ranging from 0.66. While there is still a positive relationship

between population shift and voter turnout, it's not as strong as in other districts. Nagaon stands out with a very weak positive correlation of 0.16. This indicates that there's almost no discernible relationship between population shift and voter turnout in this district over the observed time periods. Overall, these correlation coefficients indicate that there is generally a positive relationship between population shift and voter turnout in the bordering and conflict-ridden districts of Assam. Voter turnout and population change in border area districts, as well as districts where there are confrontations between the indigenous population and accused illegal immigrants, are positively correlated. The intriguing finding is that the association values are negative in the districts that do not border Bangladesh and where there has a history of lesser number of hostilities between the native population and alleged illegal immigrants. Several districts exhibit strong negative correlations, ranging from -0.84 to -1, indicating an inverse relationship between population shift and voter turnout. This suggests that as population shift increases, voter turnout tends to decrease. Notable districts in this category include Karbi Anglong, Kamrup, Kamrup (M), Nalbari, Goalpara, Morigaon, Golaghat, Jorhat, Sibsagar, Dhemaji, and Sonitpur. Particularly striking is the perfect negative correlation (-1) observed in Darrang, indicating a complete inverse relationship between population shift and voter turnout across all three time periods despite having a history of turmoil between the suspected illegal immigrants and the indigenous population in 1978. Some districts display moderate negative correlations, ranging from -0.50 to -0.73, implying a somewhat weaker but still discernible inverse relationship between population shift and voter turnout. These districts include Lakhimpur and Dibrugarh. Dima Hasao and Tinsukia exhibiting weaker negative correlations of -0.90 and -0.38 respectively. While still negative, these correlations suggest a less pronounced inverse relationship between population shift and voter turnout compared to other districts.

There is a significant link (p value $0.01 < 0.05$) between the independent and dependent variables, as indicated by a regression analysis done on the variables. The population shift in the conflict-ridden districts and districts bordering Bangladesh in Assam during the years 1991, 2001, and 2011 as a result of an increase in the number of suspected illegal immigrants is the independent variable, and the change in voter turnout in these same districts during the assembly elections in 1991, 2001, and 2011 is the dependent variable. All of the selected districts have demonstrated a substantial positive connection between the independent and

dependent variables, with the exception of Morigaon, which has experienced a significant population increase similar to the other bordering districts and also with the exception of Darang which experienced social turmoil like other conflict-ridden districts. Depending on the result, we can significantly assert that the secondary data is supporting the hypothesis that proof of citizenship through enrolling oneself into voter list is one of the factors of higher voter turnout in the bordering and conflict-ridden districts of Assam.

Conclusion:

In light of the observed demographic shifts in certain districts of Assam, the analysis of secondary data has yielded intriguing insights, suggesting a potential correlation between proof of citizenship, as demonstrated through enrolment in the voter list, and higher voter turnout in the bordering and conflict-ridden regions. The selection of districts such as Barpeta, Bongaigaon, Dhubri, Cachar, Hailakandi, Karimganj, Nagaon, Kokrajhar, and Udalguri for the study was deliberate, as these areas have witnessed significant changes in their population dynamics since 1971. The historical context of migration, both during the colonial era and post-independence, coupled with the proximity to the Bangladesh border, underscores the complexity of the demographic challenges faced by these districts. The nexus between citizenship and voter participation becomes particularly pronounced in the context of Assam's intricate socio-political landscape. Notably, Dhubri, Hailakandi, and Karimganj, with their shared borders with Bangladesh, have experienced heightened concerns regarding citizenship status, thereby making proof of citizenship a salient aspect of individual identity. Furthermore, districts like Nagaon, Barpeta, and Cachar, marked by a historical legacy of migration, continue to grapple with demographic changes, and the voter list emerges as a tangible expression of one's legal standing within the nation. The inclusion of Kokrajhar and Udalguri in the study adds another layer of complexity, as these districts have been marred by conflicts between the Muslim population and indigenous communities. In conclusion, this study provides a nuanced understanding of the relationship between proof of citizenship, as reflected in the voter behaviour in terms of voter turnout in specific districts of Assam. The findings underscore the multifaceted nature of citizenship challenges in these regions and emphasize the role of electoral participation as a mechanism for individuals to assert and validate their citizenship status amidst evolving socio-political landscapes.

Notes:

¹ Firoz Biswas et. al. (2023) Offers a qualitative understanding of the voting behaviour in Uttar Pradesh highlighting factors like communal violence sidelining developmental factors (1317-1340). Firoz Biswas (2023) observes that in the geo-cultural setting of Bihar, caste based politics is prevalent in influencing voting behaviour (655-689).

² Biren Saikia (2015) examines how illegal immigration from the neighbouring state of Bangladesh has social and economic impact on the indigenous population of Assam (58).

³ Deepankar Basu (2020) highlighted several key issues with the fundamental flaws in the National Register of Citizens (NRC) updating process in Assam and stressed the importance of creating an alternative narrative (55).

⁴ Bibhu Prasad Routray (2008) discusses the ethnic violence primarily between the Bodo tribals and Muslim settlers in two northern districts of Assam, Darang and Udalguri, which resulted in at least 55 deaths and over 100 injuries (1-4).

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